

PUBLIC VISITORS GUIDE

Indico.UN v.3
Target Audience: Public Visitors
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Contact us:
support.accreditation@un.org

UNITED NATIONS
GENEVA

CONTENTS

Introduction	1
Types of visit request	1
Accessing the visitor request interface	2
Individual visit	3
Register self as a visitor.....	3
Group visit	5
Register self as a lead visitor with companion(s).....	5
<i>STEP 1: Self registration (lead visitor)</i>	6
<i>STEP 2: Register companion(s)</i>	7
Is it possible for a lead visitor to add more companions to a group at a later date?.....	8
When a group visit request has been processed it is possible to add more companions?.....	9
Is it possible to submit a visit request for someone other than the logged in user and who is not part of a group?	9
Where can submitted visit requests be found?.....	9
What do the different statuses mean?.....	10
Can a visit request be updated?	10
Can a visit request be withdrawn?	12
What happens when a visit request is approved?.....	14
What happens when a visit request is rejected?.....	14
Customize columns on the accreditations list	15
Search requests	15

INTRODUCTION

The Public Visitors page on Indico.UN is a new component of the Access Authorization Module (AAM). It is designed to serve as a means through which the public may request a visit to the **UNHQ premises in New York**.

It is not intended for, or to be confused with, seeking formal accreditation to attend specific events.

Visitors must have an Indico account to submit and manage requests.

TYPES OF VISIT REQUEST

Individual:

- Specifically intended for a visit of **only one person**.
- The visitor must submit his/her own request and only his/her details must feature on the registration form.
- Visitor must be at least 16 years. The system will not process the request if it detects that the age of the visitor is less than 16 years.
- Approval is non-transferable.
- Visit is date specific.

Group:

- Specifically intended for a visit of **multiple persons** (min 2 up to a maximum of 20 individuals, one of whom is the group leader responsible for entering the details of all other individuals into the visit request).
- The person assuming responsibility for submitting the group visit request must be at least 18 years. The system will not process the request if it detects that the age of the person submitting the group visit request is less than 18 years.
- Requirements are as follows:
 - adults (16+ years): all data is required
 - minors (up to 16 years): only first name, last name and date of birth is required
- Approvals are non-transferable.
- Visit is date specific.

ACCESSING THE VISITOR REQUEST INTERFACE

Go to <https://indico.un.org/accreditation/> (or click **Accreditation** in the grey ribbon/breadcrumb on the interface)

First time user: read carefully the instructions available at https://indico.un.org/UNHQ/#public_visitors. Then on the right side of the page see **Apply for accreditation**, expand the first menu, and select **United Nations Headquarters**. From the second menu select **Public Visitors**. Click **Go to form**.

Return user: sees the below screen. He/she navigates it according to what he/she wants to do.

INDIVIDUAL VISIT

Register self as a visitor

!! Always have picture and copy of your Identification document ready for upload !!

Sections *Visitor details, Identification document and Access information*

Visitors who have already added some personal details to their Indico profile, this data automatically displays on the form e.g., date of birth, Id number, etc. Visitors should add any missing data and upload required attachments.

Visitors who do not have any personal details on their Indico profile should complete the form in full and upload required attachments.

Once all data and uploads have been completed, indicate the date of visit, certify, and click **Submit**.

Public Visitors Accreditation Application (for the user 'NY Visitor')

Visitor Details

Date of birth * 01/01/2000

Photo for pass *

Photo guidelines
Files accepted: .jpg, .jpeg, .png, .gif

Name must match with the Government issued ID/passport. Including special characters, accents and spaces.

First name * NY

Last name * Visitor

Email * nyvisitor@mailinator.com

The verified Indico user account email.

Identification document: passport / driving license / ID card

Must be presented when collecting the badge.

Country of issue * United States of America

Expiration date * 01/08/2033

Upload Identity *

Copy of **passport bio-pages / driving license / ID card pages** with photo, date of birth, etc.

Access Information

Proposed date of visit * 10/09/2024

Add companion

I would like to register my family or friends who will be accompanying me on this day.

* I certify that all information and documents provided are true and complete, and understand that falsification or misrepresentation could lead to denial or termination of accreditation.

A message appears on-screen acknowledging submission. The only actions that may be taken by a visitor on a pending request are either update or withdraw (see relevant sections later in this document).

✓ Accreditation 'NY Visitor' submitted successfully

Accreditation details Inactive

Full Name - NY Visitor | Badge Length - Temporary | Access Start Date - 10 Sept 2024 | Access End Date - 10 Sept 2024 #30760

Your accreditation is awaiting approval
A manager will manually validate it. Withdraw

Access dates can be adjusted by respective managers.

An email is sent to the visitor acknowledging submission.

[Indico] Accreditation for Public Visitors at United Nations Headquarters

noreply@un.org
To

Wed 14/08/2024 15:14

Dear [Name],

This message is to acknowledge receipt of your accreditation for the accreditation type **Public Visitors** under

Please note that this accreditation requires manual approval by the Secretariat. You will receive an additional email notification when your accreditation process is complete.

Accreditation Information

Name: [Name]
Office: Public Visitors
Badge: Temporary
Access Start Date: 10 Sept 2024
Access End Date: 10 Sept 2024
Note: Access dates can be adjusted by respective managers.

To manage your accreditation follow this link: [Manage my accreditation](#)

GROUP VISIT

Register self as a lead visitor with companion(s)

POINTERS

IT IS **STRONGLY ADVISED** TO:

- HAVE COPIES OF IDENTIFICATION DOCUMENTS AND PICTURES OF ALL INDIVIDUALS IN THE GROUP READY FOR UPLOAD
- HAVE TO HAND ALL DETAILS AND EMAIL ADDRESSES OF INDIVIDUALS IN THE GROUP

AN INDICO ACCOUNT IS NOT NECESSARY FOR INDIVIDUALS IN THE GROUP, ONLY THE LEAD VISITOR SUBMITTING THE REQUEST

NEVER USE THE SAME EMAIL ADDRESS FOR MORE THAN ONE GROUP MEMBER.

SYSTEM NOTIFICATIONS (E.G. APPROVAL, REJECTION, ETC.) ARE SENT TO THE EMAIL ON A FORM AND THE LEAD VISITOR SUBMITTING IT

FOR MINORS UNDER 16 YEARS, ONLY NAME AND DATE OF BIRTH IS REQUIRED ON A FORM

A LEAD VISITOR MAY HAVE NO MORE THAN 19 COMPANIONS IN HIS/HER GROUP

STEP 1: Self registration (lead visitor)

Sections *Visitor Details* and *Identification document*

As the user logged in, any personal details added to the personal profile is automatically displayed on the form e.g., date of birth, Id number, etc. Any missing data and uploads should be added.

If there are no personal details on the personal profile, complete the form in full and upload required attachments.

Ensure the two sections *Visitor details* and *Identification document* are fully completed before going any further.

Section *Access information*

Enter the date of the visit and **enable the button Add companion**. The system:

- automatically generates a name for the group e.g. Group 15
- the **Submit** button now displays as **Submit & add additional**.

Certify the form.

Click **Submit and add additional**.

Public Visitors Accreditation Application (for the user 'Newyork Visitor')

Visitor Details

Date of birth *

Photo for pass *

Photo guidelines
Files accepted: .jpg, .jpeg, .png, .gif

Name must match with the Government issued ID/passport. Including special characters, accents and spaces.

First name *

Last name *

Email *

Identification document: passport / driving license / ID card

Must be presented when collecting the badge.

Country of issue *

Expiration date *

Upload Identity * document

Copy of passport bio-pages / driving license / ID card pages with photo, date of birth, etc.

Access Information

Proposed date of visit *

Add companion

I would like to register my family or friends who will be accompanying me on this day.

Group Name *

Group name is automatically generated.

I certify that all information and documents provided are true and complete, and understand that falsification or misrepresentation could lead to denial or termination of accreditation.

Submit & add additional

STEP 2: Register companion(s)

After completing Step 1, a green message displays on screen confirming that the request for the lead visitor has been submitted.

Note that the title of the form is now “**Public Visitors Accreditation(on behalf)**”

Visitor details and Identification document

The email entered on the form must be that of the companion to receive system notifications. The lead visitor automatically receives system notifications.

An Indico account is not necessary for a companion.

NOTE: If a companion is under 16 years, only name and DoB is required. No email and ID document is required.

Section Access information

In this section:

- The group name is displayed (as attributed to the lead visitor).
- The lead visitor is identified in the *Requested by* field.

If there **ARE** more companions to add after this one being added:

- **Enable the button Add companion** (the **Submit** button now displays as **Submit & Add additional**).
- Certify the form.
- Click **Submit & Add Additional**.
- A new form opens for the next companion.

When there are no more companions to add:

- Certify the form
- Click **Submit**.

✓ Accreditation 'Newyork Visitor' submitted successfully

Public Visitors Accreditation Application(on-behalf)

Visitor Details

Date of birth *

Photo for pass *

Upload
Capture

Photo guidelines
Files accepted: .jpg, .jpeg, .png, .gif

Name must match with the Government issued ID/passport. Including special characters, accents and spaces.

First name *

Last name *

Email *

The entered email can be used to link this request to the user account, if it exists.

Identification document: passport / driving license / ID card

Must be presented when collecting the badge.

Country of issue *

Expiration date *

Upload Identity *

Upload
Capture

Copy of passport bio-pages / driving license / ID card pages with photo, date of birth, etc.

Access Information

Add companion

Add another companion?

Group *

Requested by

*

I certify that all information and documents provided are true and complete, and understand that falsification or misrepresentation could lead to denial or termination of accreditation.

Submit & add additional

Upon submission of the last companion, confirmation of his/her request is displayed on screen.

✓ Accreditation 'Coco Chanel' submitted successfully

📄 Accreditation details Inactive

Full Name - Coco Chanel | Badge Length - Temporary | Access Start Date - 2 Sept 2024 | Access End Date - 2 Sept 2024 #29142

🍃 Your accreditation is awaiting approval
 A manager will manually validate it.

➔ Withdraw

Is it possible for a lead visitor to add more companions to a group at a later date?

YES. In the *Accreditations* workspace, click the link **My groups' accreditations**. Below screenshot displays a group (numbered 15) being organised for a visit and for which there are 3 members (lead visitor + 2 others).

To add an additional member, note the group number the individual is to be added to and on the right select from the drop-down menus **United Nations Headquarters** and **Public Visitors**. Click **Request on-behalf** and **Go to form**.

Accreditations
👁️ UN organizations ▾

📄 My accreditations
📄 My accreditations on-behalf
📄 My groups' accreditations

⚙️ Customize Columns

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries

Show 15 ▾ entries

Previous
1
Next

Requested To	First Name	Last Name	Group	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge
Public Visitors	Robert	Ellis	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:06	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Newyork	Visitor	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:02	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Coco	Chanel	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:07	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary

📄 Apply for accreditation

United Nations Headquarter ▾

Public Visitors ▾

Request on-behalf
 Request for myself

➔ Go to form

A blank form opens which should be completed.

The section of importance is **Access Information**. Make sure to:

- Select the correct group number the person is to be included in.
- Certify and click **Submit**.

Access Information

Add companion Add another companion?

Group ▾

Group 8
Group 11
Group 12
Group 15

Requested by

* I certify that all information and documents provided are true and complete, and understand that falsification or misrepresentation could lead to denial or termination of accreditation.

Submit

When a group visit request has been processed it is possible to add more companions?

YES.

Is it possible to submit a visit request for someone other than the logged in user and who is not part of a group?

NO.

Where can submitted visit requests be found?

In the *Accreditations* workspace. Click **Accreditation** in the grey ribbon/breadcrumb.

My accreditations: displays the logged in user's requests.

Requested To	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge	Start Date	End Date	Events & Assignment
Public Visitors	2024/08/15 13:50	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary	2024/09/13	2024/09/13	

My accreditations on-behalf: displays requests for individuals the logged in user submitted on-behalf.

Requested To	First Name	Last Name	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge	Start Date
Public Visitors	Samson	Dingle	2024/08/15 13:53	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary	2024/09/13
Public Visitors	Peter	Simons	2024/08/15 13:51	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary	2024/09/13
Public Visitors	Coco	Chanel	2024/08/15 13:53	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary	2024/09/13

My groups' accreditations: displays requests for individuals the logged in user submitted on-behalf and the group they were assigned to.

My accreditations My accreditations on-behalf **My groups' accreditations** Customize Columns

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Show 15 entries Previous 1 Next Press enter to search

Requested To	First Name	Last Name	Group	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge
Public Visitors	Samson	Dingle	Group 6	2024/08/15 13:53	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Peter	Simons	Group 6	2024/08/15 13:51	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	NY	Visitor	Group 6	2024/08/15 13:50	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Coco	Chanel	Group 6	2024/08/15 13:53	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary

What do the different statuses mean?

- New Requests (pending processing) – for which email notifications are generated and sent to the email on the form and lead visitor (if applicable)
- On hold (pending further analysis) – for which no email notification is generated
- Pre-approved – for which no email notification is generated
- Approved – for which an email notification is generated and sent to the email on the form and lead visitor (if applicable)
- Withdrawn – for which an email notification is generated and sent to the email on the form and lead visitor (if applicable)
- Rejected – for which an email notification is generated and sent to the email on the form and the lead visitor (if applicable)

Can a visit request be updated?

**Approved requests may not be updated.
In this instance, the visitor must reach out to the UN Pass and ID Unit at UN HQ New York.**

YES but only if it is not approved yet.

In the *Accreditations* workspace click into a request on the appropriate list.

My accreditations | My accreditations on-behalf | My groups' accreditations | Customize Columns

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Show 15 entries | Previous 1 Next | Press enter to search

Requested To	First Name	Last Name	Group	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge
Public Visitors	Robert	Ellis	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:06	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Philippe	Patek	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:30	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Newyork	Visitor	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:02	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Coco	Chanel	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:07	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary

The request opens. Click the **pencil icon** in the section where an update is to be made. Remember to **SAVE**.

Visitor Details

Date of birth * 12 Jan 1980

Photo for pass *

[Photo guidelines](#)
Files accepted: .jpg, .jpeg, .png, .gif

A message appears on-screen confirming the update and indicates the concerned section.

✓ Successfully updated section "visitor_details"

An email is sent to the email address on the form (and lead visitor if applicable) confirming the update and identifies where the update took place.

[Indico] Modified Accreditation for Public Visitors at United Nations Headquarters

noreply@un.org
To: [Redacted]

Wed 14/08/2024 15:38

Dear [Redacted],

Your accreditation has been modified.

Please note that this accreditation requires manual approval by the Secretariat. You will receive an additional email notification when your accreditation process is complete.

Accreditation Information

Name: [Redacted]

Office: Public Visitors

Badge: Temporary

Access Start Date: 10 Sept 2024

Access End Date: 10 Sept 2024

Note: Access dates can be adjusted by respective managers.

Modified Section - Identification Document

Passport Expiration: 2024-0405-30

Can a visit request be withdrawn?

YES. In the *Accreditations* workspace click into a request on the appropriate list.

My accreditations | My accreditations on-behalf | **My groups' accreditations** | Customize Columns

Showing 1 to 4 of 4 entries

Show 15 entries | Previous | 1 | Next | Press enter to search

Requested To	First Name	Last Name	Group	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge
Public Visitors	Robert	Ellis	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:06	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Philippe	Patek	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:30	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Newyork	Visitor	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:02	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary
Public Visitors	Coco	Chanel	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:07	New Requests	Public Visitors	Temporary

When the details window opens click **Withdraw**.

Accreditation details Inactive

Full Name - Coco Chanel | Badge Length - Temporary | #29142
Access Start Date - 2 Sept 2024 | Access End Date - 2 Sept 2024

Your accreditation is awaiting approval
A manager will manually validate it.

A reason for withdrawal is optional. Click **Withdraw**.

Withdraw ✕

Are you sure that you want to withdraw your accreditation? This action cannot be undone.

Reason

You may provide a reason here.

Withdraw Cancel

A message appears on-screen confirming withdrawal.

Accreditation Coco Chanel successfully withdrawn

Accreditation details Inactive

Full Name - Coco Chanel | Badge Length - Temporary | #29142
Access Start Date - 2 Sept 2024 | Access End Date - 2 Sept 2024

You have withdrawn your accreditation
Contact manager if you changed your mind.

An email is sent to the email address on the form and the lead visitor (if applicable) confirming withdrawal and indicates the reasons for withdrawal (if one was provided).

[Indico] Accreditation withdrawn

noreply@un.org Reply Reply All Forward

To Wed 14/08/2024 15:38

Dear

Your accreditation for the accreditation type **Public Visitors** under is now **withdrawn**.

Reason for withdrawal: I am no longer available.

To manage your accreditation follow this link: [Manage my accreditation](#)

What happens when a visit request is approved?

An email is sent to the email address on the form and the lead visitor (if applicable).

[Indico] Accreditation approved

 noreply@un.org
To ●

☺ Reply Reply All Forward 📧 ⋮

Wed 14/08/2024 15:54

Dear

Your accreditation for the accreditation type **Public Visitors** under is now **approved**.

To manage your accreditation follow this link: [Manage my accreditation](#)

What happens when a visit request is rejected?

An email is sent to the email on the form (if applicable).

[Indico] Accreditation declined

 noreply@un.org
To ●

☺ Reply Reply All Forward 📧 ⋮

Wed 14/08/2024 16:11

Dear

We regret to inform you that Your accreditation for the accreditation type **Public Visitors** under is now **declined**.

To manage your accreditation follow this link: [Manage my accreditation](#)

CUSTOMIZE COLUMNS ON THE ACCREDITATIONS LIST

In the *Accreditations* workspace click **Customize Columns**.

The screenshot shows the 'My accreditations' workspace. At the top right, there is a 'Customize Columns' button with a gear icon, highlighted with a red rectangular box. Below the tabs, it says 'Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries'. There are navigation buttons for 'Previous', '1', and 'Next'. A search bar contains the text 'Press enter to search'. Below this is a table header with columns: Requested To, Submitted Date, Status, Accreditation Type, Pass/Badge, Start Date, End Date, and Events & Assignment.

Columns enabled on the list are displayed in blue, disabled columns are greyed out. To enable or disable a column from the list view, select it and click **Done**.

The 'Column configuration' dialog box is shown. It has a title bar with a close button. Under 'Basic Information', there are several buttons representing columns: 'Requested To', 'Submitted Date', 'Status', 'Accreditation Type', 'Pass/Badge', 'Start Date', 'End Date', 'Events & Assignment', 'Files', and 'Action'. The 'Files' and 'Action' buttons are greyed out. A 'Done' button is located at the bottom right.

Columns may also be moved on the list. Click into a column name and then drag and drop it to a new location.

The screenshot shows the 'My accreditations' workspace. The 'Customize Columns' button is highlighted. Below the table header, the 'Events & Assignment' column is highlighted with a red box. Red arrows point from the 'Start Date' and 'End Date' columns towards the 'Events & Assignment' column, indicating a drag-and-drop action.

Requested To	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge	Start Date	Events & Assignment	End Date
Public Visitors	2024/08/15 16:02	Approved	Public Visitors	Temporary	2024/09/02		2024/09/02

SEARCH REQUESTS

To search for a request, in the *Accreditations* workspace select one of the lists to search and enter a value in the search field. Press the enter/return key. The following may be used to perform a search :

- Date (format : dd/mm/yyyy)

- Status
- Event
- Accreditation type: office processing the request
- First Name (for on-behalf requests)
- Last Name (for on-behalf requests)

Click **x** to clear a search and press enter/return key.

My accreditations My accreditations on-behalf **My groups' accreditations** Customize Columns

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries (filtered from 5 total entries)

Show 15 entries Previous 1 Next Search: coco

Requested To	First Name	Last Name	Group	Submitted Date	Status	Accreditation Type	Pass/Badge
Public Visitors	Coco	Chanel	Group 15	2024/08/15 16:07	Withdrawn	Public Visitors	Temporary